

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 22

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 22

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 22:1 "My God, my God, why have You forsaken me? ^{1b}Far from my deliverance are the words of my ^{2c}groaning. ² O my God, I "cry by day, but You do not answer; And by night, but ¹I have no rest. ³ Yet "You are holy, O You who ¹are enthroned upon ^bthe praises of Israel. ⁴ In You our fathers "trusted; They trusted and You ^bdelivered them. ⁵ To You they cried out and were delivered; "In You they trusted and were not ¹disappointed.</p>	<p>לְמַנְצָחַ עַל-אַיִלַת הַשָּׁחַר מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד : ² אֱלֹהֵי אֱלֹהֵי לָמְחָה עֲזַבְתָּנִי רְחֹק מִיִּשׁוּעָתִי וּדְבַרִי שָׁאַגְתִּי : ³ אֱלֹהֵי אֶקְרָא יוֹמָם וְלֹא תִעַנֶּה וְלַיְלָה וְלֹא-דוֹמְיָה לִּי : ⁴ וְאַתָּה קָדוֹשׁ יוֹשֵׁב תְּהִלּוֹת יִשְׂרָאֵל : ⁵ בְּךָ בָּטְחוּ אֲבֹתֵינוּ בָּטְחוּ וַתִּפְלֹטְמוּ : ⁶ אֱלֹהֵיךָ זָעַקוּ וְנִמְלְטוּ בְּךָ בָּטְחוּ וְלֹא-בֹשִׁי : ⁷ וְאַנְכִי תוֹלַעַת וְלֹא- אִישׁ חֲרָפַת אָדָם וּבְזוּי עָם : ⁸ כָּל- רְאֵי יִלְעָגוּ לִי יַבְטִירוּ בְּשִׁפְחָה יִגִּיעוּ רֹאשׁ : ⁹ גֵּל אֶל-יְהוָה יִפְלֹטְהוּ יִצְלִי־הוּ כִּי תִפֶּן בּוֹ : ¹⁰ כִּי-אַתָּה גַּתִּי מִבֶּטֶן מִבְטִיחִי עַל-שָׁרֵי אֲמִי : ¹¹ עָלֶיךָ הִשְׁלַכְתִּי מִרְחָם מִבֶּטֶן אֲמִי אֱלֹהֵי אֲתָה : ¹² אֶל-תִּרְחַק מִמֶּנִּי כִּי- צָרָה קְרוּבָה כִּי-אֵין עֹזֶר : ¹³</p>
<p>Psa. 22:6 But I am a "worm and not a man, A ^breproach of men and "despised by the people. ⁷ All who see me ^{1a}sneer at me; They ²separate with the lip, they ^bwag the head, <i>saying</i>, ⁸ "Commit <i>yourself</i> to the LORD; "let Him deliver him; Let Him rescue him, because He delights in him."</p>	<p>סָבְבוּנִי פָרִים רַבִּים אַבִּירֵי בָשָׁן כִּתְרוּנִי : ¹⁴ פָּצוּ עָלַי פִּיהֶם אֲרִי־ה טָרֵף וְשָׂאג : ¹⁵ כַּמֵּים נִשְׁפַּכְתִּי וַהֲתַפְּרוּוּ כָּל-עֲצָמוֹתַי הִיָּה לְבִי כַּדוֹנֵג נָמַס בְּתוֹךְ מַעֵי : ¹⁶ יָבֵשׁ כַּחֲרָשׁ אִכְחִי וְלִשׁוֹנִי מִדְּבַק מִלְקוֹחִי וְלִעֲפָר-מָוֶת תִּשְׁפָּתֵנִי : ¹⁷</p>
<p>Psa. 22:9 Yet You are He who "brought me forth from the womb; You made me trust <i>when</i> upon my mother's breasts. ¹⁰ Upon You I was cast "from ¹birth;</p>	<p>מִלְקוֹחִי וְלִעֲפָר-מָוֶת תִּשְׁפָּתֵנִי : ¹⁷</p>

You have been my God from my mother's womb.

Psa. 22:11 "Be not far from me, for ¹trouble is near;

For there is ^bnone to help.

¹² Many ^abulls have surrounded me;
Strong *bulls* of ^bBashan have encircled me.

¹³ They ^aopen wide their mouth at me,

As a ravening and a roaring ^blion.

¹⁴ I am ^apoured out like water,
And all my ^bbones are out of joint;
My ^aheart is like wax;
It is melted within ¹me.

¹⁵ My ^astrength is dried up like a potsherd,

And ^bmy tongue cleaves to my jaws;

And You ^alay me ¹in the dust of death.

¹⁶ For ^adogs have surrounded me;
¹A band of evildoers has encompassed me;

²They ^bpierced my hands and my feet.

¹⁷ I can count all my bones.

^aThey look, they stare at me;

¹⁸ They ^adivide my garments among them,

And for my clothing they cast lots.

Psa. 22:19 But You, O LORD, ^abe not far off;

O You my help, ^bhasten to my assistance.

²⁰ Deliver my ¹soul from ^athe sword,
My ^bonly *life* from the ²power of the dog.

²¹ Save me from the ^alion's mouth;

כִּי סָבְבוּנִי כְּלָבִים עֲדַת מִרְעִים

הַקִּיפוּנִי כְּאַרְיֵי יָדַי וּרְגְלֵי : ¹⁸

אֲסַפֵּר כָּל-עֲצָמוֹתַי תְּמָה יָבִיטוּ

יְרֹאוּ-בִי : ¹⁹ יַחְלְקוּ בְגָדַי לָהֶם

וְעַל-לְבוּשֵׁי יַפְּיָלוּ גֹרְלָל : ²⁰ וְאַתָּה

יְהוָה אַל-תִּרְחַק אֵילֹוֹתַי לְעִזְרָתִי

חַוִּישָׁה : ²¹ הֲצִילָה מִתְּרַב נִפְשִׁי

מִיַּד-כָּלֵב יַחֲדָתִי : ²² הוֹשִׁיעֵנִי

מִפִּי אַרְיֵיהַ וּמִקֶּרְנֵי רַמִּים עֲנִיתָנִי :

²³ אֲסַפְּרָה שִׁמְרָה לְאַחֵי בְּתוֹךְ קִהְלָה

אֶתְהַלְלֶךָ : ²⁴ יִרְאֵי יְהוָה אֱהַלְלוּהוּ

כָּל-יֶזְרַע יַעֲקֹב כִּפְרוּהוּ וְגִוְרוּ

כַּמִּנּוֹ כָּל-יֶזְרַע יִשְׂרָאֵל : ²⁵ כִּי לֹא-

בָּזָה וְלֹא שִׁקָּץ עֵנֹוֹת עָנִי וְלֹא-

הִסְתִּיר פָּנָיו מִמִּנּוֹ וּבִשְׁוֹעוֹ אֵלָיו

שָׁמַע : ²⁶ מֵאֵתֶךָ תִּהְלָתִי בְּקִהְלָה רַב

נְדָרַי אֲשַׁלֵּם נִגְדָה יִרְאִיו : ²⁷ יֵאכְלוּ

עֲנֹוִים וְיִשְׁפְּעוּ יְהַלְלוּ יְהוָה

וְיִרְשׁוּ יַחֵי לְבַבְכֶם לְעַד : ²⁸ יִזְכְּרוּ

וְיִשְׁבּוּ אֶל-יְהוָה כָּל-אַפְסֵי-אָרֶץ

וְיִשְׁתַּחֲווּ לִפְנֵיךָ כָּל-מִשְׁפָּחוֹת

גּוֹיִם : ²⁹ כִּי לִיהוָה תִּמְלֹכָה וּמִשְׁלַל

בְּגוֹיִם : ³⁰ אֲכָלוּ וְיִשְׁתַּחֲווּ אִכְל-

וּדְשֵׁי-אָרֶץ לִפְנֵינוּ יִכְרְעוּ כָּל-

יֹוֲרָדֵי עָפָר וְנִפְשׁוּ לֹא תִיָּה : ³¹ יֶזְרַע

יַעֲבֹדֵנוּ יִסְפֹּר לְאָדָנִי לְדֹר : ³²

יָבֹאוּ וַיִּגִּידוּ צְדָקָתוֹ לְעַם נוֹלָד כִּי

עָשָׂה :

From the horns of the ^bwild oxen
You ^canswer me.

Psa. 22:22 I will ^atell of Your
name to my brethren;

In the midst of the assembly I will
praise You.

²³ ^aYou who fear the LORD, praise
Him;

All you ¹descendants of Jacob,
^bglorify Him,

And ^cstand in awe of Him, all you
¹descendants of Israel.

²⁴ For He has ^anot despised nor
abhorred the affliction of the afflicted;

Nor has He ^bhidden His face from
him;

But ^cwhen he cried to Him for
help, He heard.

Psa. 22:25 From You *comes* ^amy
praise in the great assembly;

I shall ^bpay my vows before those
who fear Him.

²⁶ The ¹afflicted will eat and ^abe
satisfied;

Those who seek Him will ^bpraise
the LORD.

Let your ^cheart live forever!

²⁷ All the ^aends of the earth will
remember and turn to the LORD,

And all the ^bfamilies of the nations
will worship before ¹You.

²⁸ For the ^akingdom is the LORD'S
And He ^brules over the nations.

²⁹ All the ^{1a}prosperous of the earth
will eat and worship,

All those who ^bgo down to the dust
will bow before Him,

Even he who ^{2c}cannot keep his
soul alive.

<p>³⁰ ^{1a}Posterity will serve Him; It will be told of the Lord to ^bthe <i>coming</i> generation.</p> <p>³¹ They will come and ^awill declare His righteousness To a people ^bwho will be born, that He has performed <i>it</i>.</p>	
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References

<p>Psalm 22:0 ¹Lit <i>the hind of the morning</i></p> <p>Psalm 22:1 ¹Or <i>Why are You so far from helping me, and from the words of my groaning?</i> ²Lit <i>roaring</i> ^aMatt 27:46; Mark 15:34 ^bPs 10:1 ^cJob 3:24; Ps 6:6; 32:3; 38:8</p> <p>Psalm 22:2 ¹Lit <i>there is no silence for me</i> ^aPs 42:3; 88:1</p> <p>Psalm 22:3 ¹Or <i>inhabit the praises</i> ^aPs 99:9 ^bDeut 10:21; Ps 148:14</p> <p>Psalm 22:4 ^aPs 78:53 ^bPs 107:6</p> <p>Psalm 22:5 ¹Or <i>ashamed</i> ^aIs 49:23</p> <p>Psalm 22:6 ^aJob 25:6; Is 41:14 ^bPs 31:11 ^cIs 49:7; 53:3</p> <p>Psalm 22:7 ¹Or <i>mock me</i> ²i.e. make mouths at me ^aPs 79:4; Is 53:3; Luke 23:35 ^bMatt 27:39; Mark 15:29</p>	<p>Psalm 22:8 ¹Lit <i>Roll</i>; another reading is <i>He committed himself</i> ^aPs 91:14; Matt 27:43</p> <p>Psalm 22:9 ^aPs 71:5, 6</p> <p>Psalm 22:10 ¹Lit <i>a womb</i> ^aIs 46:3; 49:1</p> <p>Psalm 22:11 ¹Or <i>distress</i> ^aPs 71:12 ^b2 Kin 14:26; Ps 72:12; Is 63:5</p> <p>Psalm 22:12 ^aPs 22:21; 68:30 ^bDeut 32:14; Amos 4:1</p> <p>Psalm 22:13 ^aJob 16:10; Ps 35:21; Lam 2:16; 3:46 ^bPs 10:9; 17:12</p> <p>Psalm 22:14 ¹Lit <i>my inward parts</i> ^aJob 30:16 ^bPs 31:10; Dan 5:6 ^cJosh 7:5; Job 23:16; Ps 73:26; Nah 2:10</p> <p>Psalm 22:15 ¹Lit <i>to</i> ^aPs 38:10 ^bJohn 19:28 ^cPs 104:29</p>
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Psalm 22:16

¹Or *An assembly*

²Another reading is *Like a lion, my...*

^aPs 59:6, 7

^bMatt 27:35; John 20:25

Psalm 22:17

^aLuke 23:27, 35

Psalm 22:18

^aMatt 27:35; Mark 15:24; Luke 23:34; John 19:24

Psalm 22:19

^aPs 22:11

^bPs 70:5

Psalm 22:20

¹Or *life*

²Lit *paw*

^aPs 37:14

^bPs 35:17

Psalm 22:21

^aPs 22:13

^bPs 22:12

^cPs 34:4; 118:5; 120:1

Psalm 22:22

^aPs 40:10; Heb 2:12

Psalm 22:23

¹Lit *seed*

^aPs 135:19, 20

^bPs 86:12

^cPs 33:8

Psalm 22:24

^aPs 69:33

^bPs 27:9; 69:17; 102:2

^cPs 31:22; Heb 5:7

Psalm 22:25

^aPs 35:18; 40:9, 10

^bPs 61:8; Eccl 5:4

Psalm 22:26

¹Or *poor*

^aPs 107:9

^bPs 40:16

^cPs 69:32

Psalm 22:27

¹Some versions read *Him*

^aPs 2:8; 82:8

^bPs 86:9

Psalm 22:28

^aPs 47:7; Obad 21; Zech 14:9; Matt 6:13

^bPs 47:8

Psalm 22:29

¹Lit *fat ones*

²Or *did not*

^aPs 17:10; 45:12; Hab 1:16

^bPs 28:1; Is 26:19

^cPs 89:48

Psalm 22:30

¹Lit *A seed*

^aPs 102:28

^bPs 102:18

Psalm 22:31

^aPs 40:9; 71:18

^bPs 78:6

Targum

Psa. 22:1 For praise; concerning the strength of the regular morning sacrifice; a psalm of David. ² My God, my God, why have you left me far from my redemption? – are the words of my outcry. ³ O God, I call by day and you will not accept my prayer; and by night I have no quiet ⁴ But you are holy, who make the world rest on the psalms of Israel. ⁵ Our fathers hoped in you; they hoped in your word, and you saved them. ⁶ In your presence they prayed and were saved; and on you they relied, and were not disappointed. ⁷ But I am a feeble worm, not a rational man; the reproach of the sons of men, and the butt of the Gentiles. ⁸ All who see me will gloat over me, attacking with their lips; they will shake their heads. ⁹ Let him give praise in the presence of the LORD; and he has delivered him, he saved him because he favored him. ¹⁰ Because you took me out of the womb; you gave me hope on my mother's breasts. ¹¹ By your aid I was pulled forth from [her] bowels; from my mother's womb you are my God. ¹² Be not far from me, for trouble is near, for there is no redeemer. ¹³ The Gentiles have surrounded me, who are like many bulls; the princes of Mathnan have hemmed me in. ¹⁴ They open their mouths at me like a roaring and ravaging lion. ¹⁵ Like water I am poured out; all my bones are crushed; my heart is melting like wax within my bowels. ¹⁶ My strength has dried up like a potsherd, and my tongue is stuck to my palate; and you have brought me to the grave. ¹⁷ Because the wicked have surrounded me, who are like many dogs; a gathering of evildoers has hemmed me in, biting my hands and feet like a lion. ¹⁸ I will tell of all the wounds of my bones; those who see me despise me. ¹⁹ They divide my clothing for themselves; and for my cloak they will cast lots. ²⁰ You, O LORD, do not be far off; O my strength, hurry to my aid. ²¹ Save my soul from those who slay with the sword; from the power of the dog [save] the breath of my body. ²² Redeem me from the mouth of the lion; and from kings who are strong and tall as a bull you have received my prayer. ²³ I will tell of the might of your name to my brothers; in the midst of the assembly I will praise you. ²⁴ O you who fear the LORD, sing praise in his presence; all the seed of Jacob, give him glory; and be afraid of him, all you seed of Israel. ²⁵ For he does not despise or scorn the prayer of the poor; and he has not removed his presence from their midst; and when they pray in his presence, he accepts [their prayer]. ²⁶ My psalm in the assembly of many people is from you; I will fulfill my vows before those who fear him. ²⁷ The humble will eat and be satisfied; those who seek the LORD will sing praise in his presence; the spirit of prophecy will dwell in the thoughts of your hearts forever. ²⁸ All the ends of the earth will remember his offerings and will repent in the presence of the LORD; and all the families of the Gentiles will bow down before you. ²⁹ For kingship is from the presence of the LORD, and he rules over the Gentiles. ³⁰ All who are fat on earth have eaten and bowed down; all who descend to the grave prostrate themselves before him; but the soul of the wicked shall not live. ³¹ The seed of Abraham will worship in his presence; and they will tell the mighty greatness of the

LORD to a later generation. ³² Their children will return and recount his generosity; to his people yet to be born [they will recount] the wonders he performed.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm of David deals with events destined to occur hundreds of years after David's time. He foresaw the bleak future of the Babylonian and Persian exiles. He also saw the threat of Haman and Ahasuerus against the Hebrew nation. This Psalm may have been dedicated to Queen Esther, who was the savior of the people.

When David fled from Absalom, Shimi ben Gera of the tribe of Benjamin viciously cursed David. When David's men caught him, he did not allow them to kill him. The Talmud Megilla 13a says that David foresaw that Mordecai and Esther were descendants of Shimi. For the sake of the future of David's people, he did not execute Shimi even though he had reasonable cause to do so.

Due to the length of this Psalm, a complete spiritual awareness rewrite was not done. The spiritual awareness of each verse is brought out in the analysis.

Superscript

עַל־אַיֶּלֶת הַשָּׁחַר (al-ayelet hashachar) – translated means "upon the morning star."

This phrase refers to the first visible light before the sunrise. It could have been the title of the Psalm. The English translation in the NASB 1995 is a name being assumed to be that of the choir director. Rabbi Hirsch uses the translation "upon the strengthening power of day's dawning." This Psalm thus sings of the renewed vigor which a man may derive from the knowledge that the morning brings and is not too far away.

לְמַנְצֵחַ (lam'natzecha) – translation is "choirmaster." However, it is also a call to the Sefirah Netzach. The spiritual awareness translation is "to the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory."

Verse one

David realizes that Israel's disloyalty to the LORD's Law was sufficient reason for the pain that the nation did endure (for David, it was a future of endurance of pain). Even though the LORD allowed the Assyrians and Babylonians to attack and destroy the northern ten tribes, He kept His covenant.

⁴⁴ 'Yet in spite of this, when they are in the land of their enemies, I will not reject them, nor will I so abhor them as to destroy them, breaking My covenant with them; for I am the LORD their God. (Leviticus 26:44)

David thus had a prophecy or a vision from the LORD of the future of His people.

Verse two

David's prayer for the future did not have the desired effect. It was disturbing to know this future, and it kept him up at night worrying and praying for his people.

Verse three

קָדוֹשׁ (kadosh) – means "holy." In this Psalm, this word has a deeper spiritual meaning. It is a force that is far beyond any other force in the Universe. It only belongs to the LORD. Israel is the sole spiritual bearer of kadosh's divine revelation. It is a force for the benefit of all humanity once all humanity recognizes the presence and love of the LORD

Verse four and five

Our fathers called out to the LORD and placed their faith and trust in You. In the past, LORD, you delivered them from danger. They felt reborn and had a new and better life in their arms. If you have not placed your complete faith and trust in the LORD, you can do it anytime; why not now? David realized that His faith and trust in the LORD enriched his life. He was sure that the LORD would deliver his people from the anguish of captivity and exile.

Verse six

David called himself a worm because he was scorned by men and despised among the nations that surrounded him. The revolt against David was in progress, and he had to flee into the mountains. He felt like an outlaw in his own country.

Verse seven

David refers to the people who felt that he was unworthy and would not look at his face. The people in the revolt did not want to see him alive.

Verse eight

David is expressing his inner feeling. Is he praying for the salvation of the people who want to kill him? Perhaps and if so, he is telling his enemies that they will see the ways of the LORD and come into faith and trust. If that happened, they would have stopped fighting David and instead installed him on the throne of Israel and protected him and his interests.

Verse nine and ten

The birth of the nation of Israel came to be through the favor and direction of the LORD. Up to this point (of David's reign), Israel's history was filled with difficulties and misery. So many nations of the world disappeared from history due to hardship, especially from neighbors. The LORD instructed Abraham to leave his home and extended family to travel and settle in Canaan, which was not that hospitable at the time. Since the LORD was with Abraham, he was able to establish his family there. David acknowledged this fact. Suppose the LORD did not intervene and had not gotten Joseph sent to Egypt, the family would have died of starvation. After the Egyptians decided to enslave the nation of Israel, the LORD sent Moses to rescue them. The hand of the LORD gave victory to Joshua and his army during the conquest of Canaan. The hand of the LORD was with David even in the turbulent years.

Verse eleven

David knew that he was in trouble, and he needed the hand of the LORD upon him more than ever. He felt that he had no earthly help.

Verse twelve and thirteen

פְּרִים (gareem) – translated as "bull." This term is usually employed to describe the power of nations. These verses are referring to the nations that surrounded David. These nations did not necessarily agree with each other. However, there was one thing they did agree on: they hated the Hebrew people. They acted as one mind to fight David.

Verse fourteen and fifteen

David felt that he was devoid of strength. Perhaps he tired of the continual fight against his enemies. To be poured out like water meant that he must conform to

whatever future lied ahead of him in the same way water takes the shape of the cup or surface that it is poured out on.

Verse Sixteen

David continued to describe his problems by says that dogs have surrounded him. Perhaps it is because the dogs smelled defeat on David. The symbolism is that David felt defeated. The NASB 1995 translation of the last part of this verse is incorrect. The translation says, "They pierced my hands and my feet." The Hebrew word for piercing is not in this verse. Also, the word for lion, which is in Hebrew, is not in the English translation. The proper English translation is "like lions, at my hands and feet." The Targum supports the translation not having anything to do with piercing. The Christian Church has used this Psalm as a Messianic prophecy Psalm. It is not a Messianic prophecy Psalm when examined in its original language.

The Church used the Septuagint verse, which reads: "(21:16) For many dogs have compassed me: the assembly of the wicked doers has beset me round: they pierced my hands and my feet" (Source: <https://biblehub.com/sep/psalms/22.htm>). A newer English translation which is a bit closer to the Hebrew, can be found at: <http://ccat.sas.upenn.edu/nets/edition/24-ps-nets.pdf>

Therefore, the prophecy of Jesus of Nazareth having his hands and feet nailed is based on the Greek translation of the Hebrew Scriptures that was done around 225 BCE. Since the theological position of the Church is not based on the original material, it is incorrect to use Psalm 22 as a Messianic prophetic Psalm.

Verse seventeen

Rabbi Hirsch has an entirely different translation for this verse. His translation is: "I recount to myself that whichever was and still is my strength; they behold it and look at me." Thus this verse, in this form, says that Israel, amidst the dangers and perils that it will face (and did face) will nurture the memories of its past, which was filled and upheld by the LORD. The LORD will always be with His people no matter the situation.

Verse eighteen

David said that he would freely give his enemies his material possessions. Clothing was considered a valuable commodity at that time. David knew that the LORD would ensure that he had whatever he needed to survive. Therefore, it did not matter to David that his enemies were dividing his clothing. This is another verse that the Church uses to justify the Psalm as being a messianic prophecy. It is David telling the LORD that material possession is not essential when compared to the love of the LORD.

Verse nineteen

In verse sixteen, David spoke about the dogs who were going to attack him. Symbolically the dogs are the surrounding nations and those leading the revolt. It is a cry to the LORD for help.

Verse twenty

The power against David is in the nations that surround him and in the hands of his enemies.

Verse twenty-one

David asks the LORD to be saved from the fierce animals that lived in Judea, which David was asking for the LORD's protection from his enemies.

Verse twenty-two

David said to the LORD that he will tell the people of Israel about the LORD and continue praising Him.

Verse twenty-three

David reminds us that the people who show reverence to the LORD will always offer their praise and worship to Him.

Verse twenty-four

This is another reminder from David that in the darkest days of the dispersion of the people, the LORD will always be near them,

Verse twenty-five

Anytime that David honored someone, the LORD would be praised at the same time.

Verse twenty-six

People who love the LORD and praise him will live forever with Him.

Verse twenty-seven

The people who remain "humble" before the LORD and do not seek out power and glory for themselves will be known to Him.

Verse twenty-Eight

All the kingdoms on Earth belong to the LORD. One day they will all realize this and pay homage to Him.

Verse twenty-nine

A person has to submit to the LORD's will to enjoy the pleasures and delights that the Earth and the LORD offer.

Verse thirty

In David's day, he knew that his people dedicated their lives to the LORD. In the future, David envisioned all humanity praising the LORD. Unfortunately, that day is not today.

Verse thirty-one

The current generation of elders must pass down their knowledge of the LORD to the next generation. By doing this, the name and the works of the LORD will be preserved through all eternity.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

